

Simplified procedure for zooplankton sample collection

Fabio Lepori

Département de la jeunesse, de l'environnement et de la sécurité (DJES), Direction générale de l'environnement (DGE), Section biologie des eaux. Ch. des Boveresses 155, CH-1066 Epalinges, Switzerland

**Correspondence: fabio.lepori@vd.ch*

PURPOSE

This procedure updates the zooplankton sampling method in Lake Joux, Switzerland. Until the end of 2024, the method involved sampling plankton using a vertical tow from 20 meters to the surface with a 200- μm net. This updated procedure introduces two key changes:

- **Addition of a second tow using a 64- μm net:** A second tow is now performed with a 64- μm mesh net. This finer mesh allows for the collection of smaller zooplankton (e.g., naupliar and early copepodid stages of copepods) that may be missed or underestimated when using only a 200- μm net. This addition improves data completeness and comparability with other Swiss and international monitoring programs, which typically use mesh sizes between 64 μm and 100 μm .
- **Modification of tow depth:** The tow depth is now set from 2 meters above the lake bottom (rather than fixed at 20 meters), aligning the protocol with other national and international standards. While this change is unlikely to significantly impact results during the stratified season—when deeper lake layers are often hypoxic or anoxic—it may improve detection of zooplankton inhabiting deeper waters during other times of the year.

MATERIALS

- Plankton tow net, 64- μm mesh size
- Plankton tow net, 200- μm mesh size
- Squeeze bottle filled with lake water
- 500-mL plastic watertight sample bottles (PVC or PE)
- High-grade ethanol ($\geq 95\%$)
- Field data sheet

PROCEDURE

1. Record field data

Fill out the field sheet with the following information:

- Date

- Time
 - Sampling location
 - Sampling depth (or range of depths)
 - Net mesh size
 - Net diameter
2. **Conduct two vertical tows**
 - Lower each net to 2 meters above the lake bottom (approximately 30 meters for Lake Joux) and raise it to the surface.
 - Perform the first tow with the 64- μ m net and the second with the 200- μ m net.
 - Raise the 64- μ m net at a speed of 0.5 meters per second.
 - Raise the 200- μ m net at a speed of 1 meter per second.
 3. **Rinse organisms into the cod end**
 - Once each net is lifted from the water, use a squeeze bottle filled with lake water to rinse any organisms clinging to the net into the collecting bucket (cod end).
 - Keep samples from the two tows separate.
 4. **Transfer the sample**
 - Pour the contents of the collecting bucket into the sample storage bottles.
 5. **Preserve the sample**
 - Add ethanol to the sample to reach a final concentration of at least 50%.
 6. **Store the sample**
 - Upon arrival at the laboratory, store samples in a refrigerator.
 - Within a few hours, replace the preservation solution with 80% ethanol for long-term storage.

Acknowledgements

The author thanks Nathalie Mentrety and Pierre Marles (Dpartement de la jeunesse, de l'environnement et de la scurit, Direction gnrale de l'environnement, Section Biologie des eaux, Ch. des Boveresses 155, CH-1066 Epalinges) for their valuable comments on a previous version of this document.

LITERATURE

Bledzki, L. A. and Rybak, J. I. (2016) Freshwater Crustacean Zooplankton of Europe: Cladocera & Copepoda (Calanoida, Cyclopoida). Key to species identification, with notes on ecology, distribution, methods and introduction to data analysis. Springer.

U.S. Environmental Protection Agency EPA (2013) Standard Operating Procedure for Zooplankton Sample Collection and Preservation and Secchi Depth Measurement Field Procedures. LG402. Revision 11, March 2013
<https://www.epa.gov/sites/default/files/2017-01/documents/sop-for-zooplankton-sample-collection-preservation-and-secchi-depth-measurement-field-procedures-201303-7pp.pdf>